

Analytical Report

Sample data report

New Mexico Bureau of Geology
and Mineral Resources

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Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200313
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/20/2020 11:47:13 AM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-01	Customer sample ID: ESS1	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	4280	uS/cm	1		3/25/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-01	Customer sample ID: ESS1	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.0	ph Units	1		3/24/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-01	Customer sample ID: ESS1	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	236	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.02 (0.2)	4/2/2020
Magnesium	91.8	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Potassium	23.6	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Silicon	15.7	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	4/2/2020
Sodium	591	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Strontium	4.40	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-01	Customer sample ID: ESS1	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Barium	0.021	mg/L	10	0.001 (0.01)	4/3/2020

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Beryllium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Boron 11	0.486	mg/L	10	0.005	(0.05)	4/3/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Copper 65	0.0065	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.01	(0.1)	4/3/2020
Lead	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Lithium	0.196	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Manganese	0.099	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.014	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Silicon	16.5	mg/L	10	0.02	(0.2)	4/3/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Strontium	4.65	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Uranium	0.0135	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Vanadium	0.0053	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Zinc 66	0.0058	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-01	Customer sample ID: ESS1	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	0.61	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/1/2020
Chloride	875	mg/L	10	1 (10)	4/1/2020
Fluoride	1.86	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/1/2020
Nitrate	ND	mg NO3/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/1/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/1/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	5	0.5 (2.5)	4/1/2020
Sulfate	873	mg/L	10	1 (10)	4/1/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200313
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	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-01	Customer sample ID: ESS1	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	250	mg/L	1	5	3/24/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	305	mg/L	1	5	3/24/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	3/24/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-01	Customer sample ID: ESS1	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	48.01	meq/L	1		
Cations total	45.67	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	-2.50	%	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-01	Customer sample ID: ESS1	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	968	mg CaCO3/ L	1		

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200313
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	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-02	Customer sample ID: ESS2	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	4200	uS/cm	1		3/25/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-02	Customer sample ID: ESS2	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.0	ph Units	1		3/24/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-02	Customer sample ID: ESS2	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	245	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.02 (0.2)	4/2/2020
Magnesium	96.3	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Potassium	24.5	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Silicon	17.7	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	4/2/2020
Sodium	619	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Strontium	4.52	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-02	Customer sample ID: ESS2	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Barium	0.020	mg/L	10	0.001 (0.01)	4/3/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Boron 11	0.463	mg/L	10	0.005 (0.05)	4/3/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Copper 65	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	4/3/2020

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Lead	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Lithium	0.189	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Manganese	0.150	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.014	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Silicon	18.1	mg/L	10	0.02	(0.2)	4/3/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Strontium	4.50	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Uranium	0.0128	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Vanadium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Zinc 66	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-02	Customer sample ID: ESS2	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	ND	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/1/2020
Chloride	870	mg/L	10	1 (10)	4/1/2020
Fluoride	1.88	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/1/2020
Nitrate	ND	mg NO3/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/1/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/1/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	5	0.5 (2.5)	4/1/2020
Sulfate	855	mg/L	10	1 (10)	4/1/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-02	Customer sample ID: ESS2	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	260	mg/L	1	5	3/24/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	317	mg/L	1	5	3/24/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	3/24/2020

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	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-02	Customer sample ID: ESS2	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	47.68	meq/L	1		
Cations total	47.73	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	0.05	%	1		
SiO2	36.9	mg/L	1	0.05	
TDS calc	2910	mg/L	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-02	Customer sample ID: ESS2	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	1010	mg CaCO3/ L	1		

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200313
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/20/2020 11:47:13 AM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-03	Customer sample ID: ESS3	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	4280	uS/cm	1		3/25/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-03	Customer sample ID: ESS3	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	7.9	ph Units	1		3/24/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-03	Customer sample ID: ESS3	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	232	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.02 (0.2)	4/2/2020
Magnesium	89.7	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Potassium	22.9	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Silicon	16.0	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	4/2/2020
Sodium	588	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Strontium	4.41	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-03	Customer sample ID: ESS3	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Barium	0.020	mg/L	10	0.001 (0.01)	4/3/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Boron 11	0.477	mg/L	10	0.005 (0.05)	4/3/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Copper 65	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	4/3/2020

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	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Lithium	0.193	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Manganese	0.148	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.015	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Silicon	17.0	mg/L	10	0.02	(0.2)	4/3/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Strontium	4.65	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Uranium	0.0132	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Vanadium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Zinc 66	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-03	Customer sample ID: ESS3	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	0.56	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/1/2020
Chloride	865	mg/L	10	1 (10)	4/1/2020
Fluoride	1.91	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/1/2020
Nitrate	ND	mg NO3/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/1/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/1/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	5	0.5 (2.5)	4/1/2020
Sulfate	862	mg/L	10	1 (10)	4/1/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-03	Customer sample ID: ESS3	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	258	mg/L	1	5	3/24/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	315	mg/L	1	5	3/24/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	3/24/2020

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	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-03	Customer sample ID: ESS3	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	47.65	meq/L	1		
Cations total	45.13	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	-2.71	%	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-03	Customer sample ID: ESS3	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	949	mg CaCO3/ L	1		

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200313
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	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-04	Customer sample ID: ESS4	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	4280	uS/cm	1		3/25/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-04	Customer sample ID: ESS4	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.2	ph Units	1		3/24/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-04	Customer sample ID: ESS4	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	237	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.02 (0.2)	4/2/2020
Magnesium	90.2	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Potassium	22.8	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Silicon	15.7	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	4/2/2020
Sodium	591	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Strontium	4.45	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-04	Customer sample ID: ESS4	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Barium	0.018	mg/L	10	0.001 (0.01)	4/3/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Boron 11	0.479	mg/L	10	0.005 (0.05)	4/3/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Copper 65	0.0054	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	4/3/2020

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Lead	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Lithium	0.189	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Manganese	0.096	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.013	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Silicon	16.3	mg/L	10	0.02	(0.2)	4/3/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Strontium	4.64	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Uranium	0.0130	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Vanadium	0.0053	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Zinc 66	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-04	Customer sample ID: ESS4	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	ND	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/1/2020
Chloride	866	mg/L	10	1 (10)	4/1/2020
Fluoride	1.90	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/1/2020
Nitrate	ND	mg NO3/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/1/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/1/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	5	0.5 (2.5)	4/1/2020
Sulfate	864	mg/L	10	1 (10)	4/1/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-04	Customer sample ID: ESS4	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	267	mg/L	1	5	3/24/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	326	mg/L	1	5	3/24/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	3/24/2020

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	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-04	Customer sample ID: ESS4	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	47.87	meq/L	1		
Cations total	45.56	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	-2.48	%	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-04	Customer sample ID: ESS4	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	964	mg CaCO3/ L	1		

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200313
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/20/2020 11:47:13 AM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-05	Customer sample ID: ESS5	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	4280	uS/cm	1		3/25/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-05	Customer sample ID: ESS5	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	7.9	ph Units	1		3/24/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-05	Customer sample ID: ESS5	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	257	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.02 (0.2)	4/2/2020
Magnesium	95.0	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Potassium	24.3	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Silicon	15.6	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	4/2/2020
Sodium	621	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Strontium	4.64	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-05	Customer sample ID: ESS5	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Barium	0.018	mg/L	10	0.001 (0.01)	4/3/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Boron 11	0.486	mg/L	10	0.005 (0.05)	4/3/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Copper 65	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	4/3/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200313
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/20/2020 11:47:13 AM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Lithium	0.189	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Manganese	0.107	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.013	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Silicon	16.0	mg/L	10	0.02	(0.2)	4/3/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Strontium	4.73	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Uranium	0.0129	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Vanadium	0.0052	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Zinc 66	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-05	Customer sample ID: ESS5	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	0.62	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/1/2020
Chloride	867	mg/L	10	1 (10)	4/1/2020
Fluoride	1.90	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/1/2020
Nitrate	ND	mg NO3/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/1/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/1/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	5	0.5 (2.5)	4/1/2020
Sulfate	867	mg/L	10	1 (10)	4/1/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-05	Customer sample ID: ESS5	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	274	mg/L	1	5	3/24/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	335	mg/L	1	5	3/24/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	3/24/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200313
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/20/2020 11:47:13 AM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-05	Customer sample ID: ESS5	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	48.14	meq/L	1		
Cations total	48.28	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	0.14	%	1		
SiO2	31.6	mg/L	1	0.05	
TDS calc	2940	mg/L	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-05	Customer sample ID: ESS5	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	1030	mg CaCO3/ L	1		

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200313
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/20/2020 11:47:13 AM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-06	Customer sample ID: ESS6	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	4280	uS/cm	1		3/25/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-06	Customer sample ID: ESS6	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.2	ph Units	1		3/24/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-06	Customer sample ID: ESS6	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	243	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.02 (0.2)	4/2/2020
Magnesium	92.0	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Potassium	23.5	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Silicon	15.0	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	4/2/2020
Sodium	597	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Strontium	4.51	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-06	Customer sample ID: ESS6	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Barium	0.018	mg/L	10	0.001 (0.01)	4/3/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Boron 11	0.498	mg/L	10	0.005 (0.05)	4/3/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Copper 65	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	4/3/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200313
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/20/2020 11:47:13 AM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Lithium	0.194	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Manganese	0.050	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.012	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Silicon	15.8	mg/L	10	0.02	(0.2)	4/3/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Strontium	4.78	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Uranium	0.0126	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Vanadium	0.0055	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Zinc 66	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-06	Customer sample ID: ESS6	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	0.55	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/1/2020
Chloride	876	mg/L	10	1 (10)	4/1/2020
Fluoride	1.88	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/1/2020
Nitrate	ND	mg NO3/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/1/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/1/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	5	0.5 (2.5)	4/1/2020
Sulfate	878	mg/L	10	1 (10)	4/1/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-06	Customer sample ID: ESS6	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	278	mg/L	1	5	3/24/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	339	mg/L	1	5	3/24/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	3/24/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200313
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/20/2020 11:47:13 AM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-06	Customer sample ID: ESS6	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	48.64	meq/L	1		
Cations total	46.28	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	-2.48	%	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-06	Customer sample ID: ESS6	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	986	mg CaCO3/ L	1		

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200313
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/20/2020 11:47:13 AM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-07	Customer sample ID: SS1	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	1970	uS/cm	1		3/25/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-07	Customer sample ID: SS1	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.5	ph Units	1		3/24/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-07	Customer sample ID: SS1	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	117	mg/L	5	0.05 (0.25)	4/2/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	5	0.02 (0.1)	4/2/2020
Magnesium	41.1	mg/L	5	0.05 (0.25)	4/2/2020
Potassium	14.0	mg/L	5	0.05 (0.25)	4/2/2020
Silicon	10.6	mg/L	5	0.01 (0.05)	4/2/2020
Sodium	249	mg/L	5	0.05 (0.25)	4/2/2020
Strontium	2.05	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	4/2/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-07	Customer sample ID: SS1	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	4/3/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	4/3/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	4/3/2020
Barium	0.035	mg/L	5	0.001 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	4/3/2020
Boron 11	0.221	mg/L	5	0.005 (0.025)	4/3/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	4/3/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	4/3/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	4/3/2020
Copper 65	0.0036	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	4/3/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	5	0.01 (0.05)	4/3/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200313
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/20/2020 11:47:13 AM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	4/3/2020
Lithium	0.093	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.010	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	4/3/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Silicon	11.4	mg/L	5	0.02	(0.1)	4/3/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	4/3/2020
Strontium	2.17	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	4/3/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	4/3/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	4/3/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Uranium	0.0038	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	4/3/2020
Vanadium	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	4/3/2020
Zinc 66	0.0038	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	4/3/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-07	Customer sample ID: SS1	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	0.18	mg/L	1	0.1	4/1/2020
Chloride	293	mg/L	5	1 (5)	4/1/2020
Fluoride	1.21	mg/L	1	0.1	4/1/2020
Nitrate	0.12	mg NO3/L	1	0.1	4/1/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	1	0.1	4/1/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	1	0.5	4/1/2020
Sulfate	331	mg/L	5	1 (5)	4/1/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-07	Customer sample ID: SS1	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	280	mg/L	1	5	3/24/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	336	mg/L	1	5	3/24/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	3/24/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200313
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/20/2020 11:47:13 AM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-07	Customer sample ID: SS1	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	20.85	meq/L	1		
Cations total	20.40	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	-1.09	%	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-07	Customer sample ID: SS1	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	462	mg CaCO3/ L	1		

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200313
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/20/2020 11:47:13 AM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-08	Customer sample ID: SS2	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	1900	uS/cm	1		3/25/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-08	Customer sample ID: SS2	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.2	ph Units	1		3/24/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-08	Customer sample ID: SS2	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	118	mg/L	5	0.05 (0.25)	4/2/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	5	0.02 (0.1)	4/2/2020
Magnesium	40.8	mg/L	5	0.05 (0.25)	4/2/2020
Potassium	14.0	mg/L	5	0.05 (0.25)	4/2/2020
Silicon	10.3	mg/L	5	0.01 (0.05)	4/2/2020
Sodium	246	mg/L	5	0.05 (0.25)	4/2/2020
Strontium	2.06	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	4/2/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-08	Customer sample ID: SS2	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	4/3/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	4/3/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	4/3/2020
Barium	0.034	mg/L	5	0.001 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	4/3/2020
Boron 11	0.207	mg/L	5	0.005 (0.025)	4/3/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	4/3/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	4/3/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	4/3/2020
Copper 65	0.0030	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	4/3/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	5	0.01 (0.05)	4/3/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200313
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/20/2020 11:47:13 AM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	4/3/2020
Lithium	0.090	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.010	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	4/3/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Silicon	10.9	mg/L	5	0.02	(0.1)	4/3/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	4/3/2020
Strontium	2.11	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	4/3/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	4/3/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	4/3/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Uranium	0.0037	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	4/3/2020
Vanadium	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	4/3/2020
Zinc 66	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	4/3/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-08	Customer sample ID: SS2	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	0.15	mg/L	1	0.1	4/1/2020
Chloride	282	mg/L	5	1 (5)	4/1/2020
Fluoride	1.21	mg/L	1	0.1	4/1/2020
Nitrate	0.11	mg NO3/L	1	0.1	4/1/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	1	0.1	4/1/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	1	0.5	4/1/2020
Sulfate	317	mg/L	5	1 (5)	4/1/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-08	Customer sample ID: SS2	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	266	mg/L	1	5	3/24/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	324	mg/L	1	5	3/24/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	3/24/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200313
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/20/2020 11:47:13 AM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-08	Customer sample ID: SS2	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	19.94	meq/L	1		
Cations total	20.31	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	0.91	%	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-08	Customer sample ID: SS2	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	462	mg CaCO3/ L	1		

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200313
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/20/2020 11:47:13 AM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-09	Customer sample ID: SS3	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	1910	uS/cm	1		3/25/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-09	Customer sample ID: SS3	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.2	ph Units	1		3/24/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-09	Customer sample ID: SS3	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	115	mg/L	5	0.05 (0.25)	4/2/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	5	0.02 (0.1)	4/2/2020
Magnesium	42.3	mg/L	5	0.05 (0.25)	4/2/2020
Potassium	14.4	mg/L	5	0.05 (0.25)	4/2/2020
Silicon	11.2	mg/L	5	0.01 (0.05)	4/2/2020
Sodium	254	mg/L	5	0.05 (0.25)	4/2/2020
Strontium	2.07	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	4/2/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-09	Customer sample ID: SS3	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	0.0026	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	4/3/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	4/3/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	4/3/2020
Barium	0.029	mg/L	5	0.001 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	4/3/2020
Boron 11	0.209	mg/L	5	0.005 (0.025)	4/3/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	4/3/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	4/3/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	4/3/2020
Copper 65	0.0030	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	4/3/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	5	0.01 (0.05)	4/3/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200313
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/20/2020 11:47:13 AM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	4/3/2020
Lithium	0.093	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.010	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	4/3/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Silicon	11.7	mg/L	5	0.02	(0.1)	4/3/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	4/3/2020
Strontium	2.11	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	4/3/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	4/3/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	4/3/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Uranium	0.0034	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	4/3/2020
Vanadium	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	4/3/2020
Zinc 66	0.0032	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	4/3/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-09	Customer sample ID: SS3	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	0.16	mg/L	1	0.1	4/1/2020
Chloride	292	mg/L	5	1 (5)	4/1/2020
Fluoride	1.23	mg/L	1	0.1	4/1/2020
Nitrate	0.13	mg NO3/L	1	0.1	4/1/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	1	0.1	4/1/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	1	0.5	4/1/2020
Sulfate	326	mg/L	5	1 (5)	4/1/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-09	Customer sample ID: SS3	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	253	mg/L	1	5	3/24/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	308	mg/L	1	5	3/24/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	3/24/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200313
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/20/2020 11:47:13 AM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-09	Customer sample ID: SS3	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	20.16	meq/L	1		
Cations total	20.59	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	1.06	%	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-09	Customer sample ID: SS3	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	460	mg CaCO3/ L	1		

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200313
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/20/2020 11:47:13 AM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-10	Customer sample ID: SS4	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	1960	uS/cm	1		3/25/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-10	Customer sample ID: SS4	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.4	ph Units	1		3/24/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-10	Customer sample ID: SS4	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	114	mg/L	5	0.05 (0.25)	4/2/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	5	0.02 (0.1)	4/2/2020
Magnesium	41.9	mg/L	5	0.05 (0.25)	4/2/2020
Potassium	14.2	mg/L	5	0.05 (0.25)	4/2/2020
Silicon	10.8	mg/L	5	0.01 (0.05)	4/2/2020
Sodium	249	mg/L	5	0.05 (0.25)	4/2/2020
Strontium	2.07	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	4/2/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-10	Customer sample ID: SS4	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	4/3/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	4/3/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	4/3/2020
Barium	0.028	mg/L	5	0.001 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	4/3/2020
Boron 11	0.211	mg/L	5	0.005 (0.025)	4/3/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	4/3/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	4/3/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	4/3/2020
Copper 65	0.0027	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	4/3/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	5	0.01 (0.05)	4/3/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200313
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/20/2020 11:47:13 AM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	4/3/2020
Lithium	0.089	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.009	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	4/3/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Silicon	11.1	mg/L	5	0.02	(0.1)	4/3/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	4/3/2020
Strontium	2.16	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	4/3/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	4/3/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	4/3/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Uranium	0.0036	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	4/3/2020
Vanadium	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	4/3/2020
Zinc 66	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	4/3/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-10	Customer sample ID: SS4	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	0.18	mg/L	1	0.1	4/1/2020
Chloride	300	mg/L	5	1 (5)	4/1/2020
Fluoride	1.23	mg/L	1	0.1	4/1/2020
Nitrate	0.15	mg NO3/L	1	0.1	4/1/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	1	0.1	4/1/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	1	0.5	4/1/2020
Sulfate	330	mg/L	5	1 (5)	4/1/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-10	Customer sample ID: SS4	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	260	mg/L	1	5	3/24/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	314	mg/L	1	5	3/24/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	3/24/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200313
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/20/2020 11:47:13 AM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-10	Customer sample ID: SS4	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	20.60	meq/L	1		
Cations total	20.35	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	-0.63	%	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-10	Customer sample ID: SS4	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	457	mg CaCO3/ L	1		

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200313
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/20/2020 11:47:13 AM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-11	Customer sample ID: SS5	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	1980	uS/cm	1		3/25/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-11	Customer sample ID: SS5	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.2	ph Units	1		3/24/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-11	Customer sample ID: SS5	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	119	mg/L	5	0.05 (0.25)	4/2/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	5	0.02 (0.1)	4/2/2020
Magnesium	43.0	mg/L	5	0.05 (0.25)	4/2/2020
Potassium	15.2	mg/L	5	0.05 (0.25)	4/2/2020
Silicon	10.7	mg/L	5	0.01 (0.05)	4/2/2020
Sodium	256	mg/L	5	0.05 (0.25)	4/2/2020
Strontium	2.13	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	4/2/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-11	Customer sample ID: SS5	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	4/3/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	4/3/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	4/3/2020
Barium	0.041	mg/L	5	0.001 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	4/3/2020
Boron 11	0.227	mg/L	5	0.005 (0.025)	4/3/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	4/3/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	4/3/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	4/3/2020
Copper 65	0.0052	mg/L	5	0.0005 (0.0025)	4/3/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	5	0.01 (0.05)	4/3/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200313
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/20/2020 11:47:13 AM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	4/3/2020
Lithium	0.092	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.010	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	4/3/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Silicon	11.3	mg/L	5	0.02	(0.1)	4/3/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	4/3/2020
Strontium	2.21	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	4/3/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	4/3/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	4/3/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	5	0.001	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Uranium	0.0039	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	4/3/2020
Vanadium	ND	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	4/3/2020
Zinc 66	0.0040	mg/L	5	0.0005	(0.0025)	4/3/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-11	Customer sample ID: SS5	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	0.17	mg/L	1	0.1	4/1/2020
Chloride	306	mg/L	5	1 (5)	4/1/2020
Fluoride	1.24	mg/L	1	0.1	4/1/2020
Nitrate	0.10	mg NO3/L	1	0.1	4/1/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	1	0.1	4/1/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	1	0.5	4/1/2020
Sulfate	334	mg/L	5	1 (5)	4/1/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-11	Customer sample ID: SS5	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	267	mg/L	1	5	3/24/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	325	mg/L	1	5	3/24/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	3/24/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200313
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/20/2020 11:47:13 AM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-11	Customer sample ID: SS5	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	20.98	meq/L	1		
Cations total	20.98	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	0.01	%	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-11	Customer sample ID: SS5	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	474	mg CaCO3/ L	1		

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200313
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/20/2020 11:47:13 AM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-12	Customer sample ID: GS1	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	3240	uS/cm	1		3/25/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-12	Customer sample ID: GS1	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.3	ph Units	1		3/24/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-12	Customer sample ID: GS1	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	177	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.02 (0.2)	4/2/2020
Magnesium	79.7	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Potassium	19.0	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Silicon	8.84	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	4/2/2020
Sodium	445	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Strontium	3.50	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-12	Customer sample ID: GS1	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Barium	0.019	mg/L	10	0.001 (0.01)	4/3/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Boron 11	0.392	mg/L	10	0.005 (0.05)	4/3/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Copper 65	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	4/3/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200313
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/20/2020 11:47:13 AM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Lithium	0.164	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.010	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Silicon	9.46	mg/L	10	0.02	(0.2)	4/3/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Strontium	3.54	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Uranium	0.0055	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Vanadium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Zinc 66	0.0117	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-12	Customer sample ID: GS1	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	ND	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/1/2020
Chloride	638	mg/L	10	1 (10)	4/1/2020
Fluoride	1.54	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/1/2020
Nitrate	0.58	mg NO3/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/1/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/1/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	5	0.5 (2.5)	4/1/2020
Sulfate	655	mg/L	10	1 (10)	4/1/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-12	Customer sample ID: GS1	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	227	mg/L	1	5	3/24/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	277	mg/L	1	5	3/24/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	3/24/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200313
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/20/2020 11:47:13 AM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-12	Customer sample ID: GS1	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	36.30	meq/L	1		
Cations total	35.22	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	-1.51	%	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-12	Customer sample ID: GS1	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	770	mg CaCO3/ L	1		

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200313
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/20/2020 11:47:13 AM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-13	Customer sample ID: GS2	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	3250	uS/cm	1		3/25/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-13	Customer sample ID: GS2	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.2	ph Units	1		3/24/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-13	Customer sample ID: GS2	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	175	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.02 (0.2)	4/2/2020
Magnesium	79.3	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Potassium	18.8	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Silicon	8.78	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	4/2/2020
Sodium	437	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Strontium	3.44	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-13	Customer sample ID: GS2	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Barium	0.020	mg/L	10	0.001 (0.01)	4/3/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Boron 11	0.390	mg/L	10	0.005 (0.05)	4/3/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Copper 65	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	4/3/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200313
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/20/2020 11:47:13 AM
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	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Lithium	0.158	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.010	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Silicon	9.54	mg/L	10	0.02	(0.2)	4/3/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Strontium	3.54	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Uranium	0.0054	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Vanadium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Zinc 66	0.0111	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-13	Customer sample ID: GS2	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	ND	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/1/2020
Chloride	640	mg/L	10	1 (10)	4/1/2020
Fluoride	1.61	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/1/2020
Nitrate	0.74	mg NO3/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/1/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/1/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	5	0.5 (2.5)	4/1/2020
Sulfate	659	mg/L	10	1 (10)	4/1/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-13	Customer sample ID: GS2	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	227	mg/L	1	5	3/24/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	277	mg/L	1	5	3/24/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	3/24/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200313
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/20/2020 11:47:13 AM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-13	Customer sample ID: GS2	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	36.45	meq/L	1		
Cations total	34.79	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	-2.34	%	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-13	Customer sample ID: GS2	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	765	mg CaCO3/ L	1		

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200313
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/20/2020 11:47:13 AM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-14	Customer sample ID: GS3	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	3230	uS/cm	1		3/25/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-14	Customer sample ID: GS3	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.3	ph Units	1		3/24/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-14	Customer sample ID: GS3	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	173	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.02 (0.2)	4/2/2020
Magnesium	80.1	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Potassium	19.2	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Silicon	9.08	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	4/2/2020
Sodium	448	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Strontium	3.49	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-14	Customer sample ID: GS3	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Barium	0.018	mg/L	10	0.001 (0.01)	4/3/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Boron 11	0.390	mg/L	10	0.005 (0.05)	4/3/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Copper 65	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	4/3/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200313
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/20/2020 11:47:13 AM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Lithium	0.152	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.010	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Silicon	9.61	mg/L	10	0.02	(0.2)	4/3/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Strontium	3.47	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Uranium	0.0053	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Vanadium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Zinc 66	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-14	Customer sample ID: GS3	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	0.54	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/1/2020
Chloride	642	mg/L	10	1 (10)	4/1/2020
Fluoride	1.54	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/1/2020
Nitrate	0.76	mg NO3/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/1/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/1/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	5	0.5 (2.5)	4/1/2020
Sulfate	658	mg/L	10	1 (10)	4/1/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-14	Customer sample ID: GS3	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	216	mg/L	1	5	3/24/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	263	mg/L	1	5	3/24/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	3/24/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200313
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/20/2020 11:47:13 AM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-14	Customer sample ID: GS3	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	36.22	meq/L	1		
Cations total	35.20	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	-1.42	%	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-14	Customer sample ID: GS3	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	762	mg CaCO3/ L	1		

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200313
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/20/2020 11:47:13 AM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-15	Customer sample ID: GS4	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	3270	uS/cm	1		3/25/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-15	Customer sample ID: GS4	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.2	ph Units	1		3/24/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-15	Customer sample ID: GS4	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	182	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.02 (0.2)	4/2/2020
Magnesium	81.5	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Potassium	19.5	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Silicon	9.04	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	4/2/2020
Sodium	448	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Strontium	3.46	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-15	Customer sample ID: GS4	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Barium	0.020	mg/L	10	0.001 (0.01)	4/3/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Boron 11	0.389	mg/L	10	0.005 (0.05)	4/3/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Copper 65	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	4/3/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200313
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/20/2020 11:47:13 AM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Lithium	0.162	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.010	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Silicon	9.88	mg/L	10	0.02	(0.2)	4/3/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Strontium	3.67	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Uranium	0.0053	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Vanadium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Zinc 66	0.0082	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-15	Customer sample ID: GS4	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	ND	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/1/2020
Chloride	637	mg/L	10	1 (10)	4/1/2020
Fluoride	1.52	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/1/2020
Nitrate	ND	mg NO3/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/1/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/1/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	5	0.5 (2.5)	4/1/2020
Sulfate	653	mg/L	10	1 (10)	4/1/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-15	Customer sample ID: GS4	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	234	mg/L	1	5	3/24/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	285	mg/L	1	5	3/24/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	3/24/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200313
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/20/2020 11:47:13 AM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-15	Customer sample ID: GS4	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	36.36	meq/L	1		
Cations total	35.77	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	-0.82	%	1		
SiO2	16.0	mg/L	1	0.05	
TDS calc	2190	mg/L	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-15	Customer sample ID: GS4	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	791	mg CaCO3/ L	1		

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200313
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/20/2020 11:47:13 AM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-16	Customer sample ID: GS5	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	3250	uS/cm	1		3/25/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-16	Customer sample ID: GS5	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.2	ph Units	1		3/24/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-16	Customer sample ID: GS5	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	170	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.02 (0.2)	4/2/2020
Magnesium	78.3	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Potassium	18.7	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Silicon	8.84	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	4/2/2020
Sodium	442	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Strontium	3.44	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-16	Customer sample ID: GS5	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Barium	0.019	mg/L	10	0.001 (0.01)	4/3/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Boron 11	0.389	mg/L	10	0.005 (0.05)	4/3/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Copper 65	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	4/3/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200313
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/20/2020 11:47:13 AM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Lithium	0.148	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.010	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Silicon	9.38	mg/L	10	0.02	(0.2)	4/3/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Strontium	3.50	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Uranium	0.0054	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Vanadium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Zinc 66	0.0078	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-16	Customer sample ID: GS5	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	ND	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/1/2020
Chloride	635	mg/L	10	1 (10)	4/1/2020
Fluoride	1.56	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/1/2020
Nitrate	0.68	mg NO3/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/1/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/1/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	5	0.5 (2.5)	4/1/2020
Sulfate	651	mg/L	10	1 (10)	4/1/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-16	Customer sample ID: GS5	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	221	mg/L	1	5	3/24/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	269	mg/L	1	5	3/24/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	3/24/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200313
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/20/2020 11:47:13 AM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-16	Customer sample ID: GS5	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	35.97	meq/L	1		
Cations total	34.62	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	-1.91	%	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-16	Customer sample ID: GS5	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	746	mg CaCO3/ L	1		

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200313
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/20/2020 11:47:13 AM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-17	Customer sample ID: GS6	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	3230	uS/cm	1		3/25/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-17	Customer sample ID: GS6	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.3	ph Units	1		3/24/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-17	Customer sample ID: GS6	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	169	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.02 (0.2)	4/2/2020
Magnesium	77.5	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Potassium	18.4	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Silicon	8.72	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	4/2/2020
Sodium	434	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Strontium	3.39	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-17	Customer sample ID: GS6	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Barium	0.019	mg/L	10	0.001 (0.01)	4/3/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Boron 11	0.394	mg/L	10	0.005 (0.05)	4/3/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Copper 65	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	4/3/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200313
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/20/2020 11:47:13 AM
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	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Lithium	0.155	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.010	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Silicon	9.58	mg/L	10	0.02	(0.2)	4/3/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Strontium	3.54	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Uranium	0.0053	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Vanadium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Zinc 66	0.0145	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-17	Customer sample ID: GS6	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	ND	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/1/2020
Chloride	634	mg/L	10	1 (10)	4/1/2020
Fluoride	1.54	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/1/2020
Nitrate	0.60	mg NO3/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/1/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/1/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	5	0.5 (2.5)	4/1/2020
Sulfate	650	mg/L	10	1 (10)	4/1/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-17	Customer sample ID: GS6	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	224	mg/L	1	5	3/24/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	274	mg/L	1	5	3/24/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	3/24/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200313
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/20/2020 11:47:13 AM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-17	Customer sample ID: GS6	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	36.02	meq/L	1		
Cations total	34.17	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	-2.63	%	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-17	Customer sample ID: GS6	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	741	mg CaCO3/ L	1		

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200313
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/20/2020 11:47:13 AM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-18	Customer sample ID: SSS1	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	3250	uS/cm	1		3/25/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-18	Customer sample ID: SSS1	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.2	ph Units	1		3/24/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-18	Customer sample ID: SSS1	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	174	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.02 (0.2)	4/2/2020
Magnesium	78.7	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Potassium	18.6	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Silicon	10.4	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	4/2/2020
Sodium	440	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Strontium	3.42	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-18	Customer sample ID: SSS1	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Barium	0.021	mg/L	10	0.001 (0.01)	4/3/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Boron 11	0.399	mg/L	10	0.005 (0.05)	4/3/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Copper 65	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	4/3/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200313
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/20/2020 11:47:13 AM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Lithium	0.157	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.010	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Silicon	11.0	mg/L	10	0.02	(0.2)	4/3/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Strontium	3.58	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Uranium	0.0059	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Vanadium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Zinc 66	0.0099	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-18	Customer sample ID: SSS1	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	ND	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/1/2020
Chloride	635	mg/L	10	1 (10)	4/1/2020
Fluoride	1.51	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/1/2020
Nitrate	0.58	mg NO3/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/1/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/1/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	5	0.5 (2.5)	4/1/2020
Sulfate	652	mg/L	10	1 (10)	4/1/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-18	Customer sample ID: SSS1	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	230	mg/L	1	5	3/24/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	281	mg/L	1	5	3/24/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	3/24/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200313
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/20/2020 11:47:13 AM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-18	Customer sample ID: SSS1	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	36.21	meq/L	1		
Cations total	34.78	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	-2.01	%	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-18	Customer sample ID: SSS1	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	760	mg CaCO3/ L	1		

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200313
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/20/2020 11:47:13 AM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-19	Customer sample ID: SSS2	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	3260	uS/cm	1		3/25/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-19	Customer sample ID: SSS2	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.0	ph Units	1		3/24/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-19	Customer sample ID: SSS2	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	177	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.02 (0.2)	4/2/2020
Magnesium	79.7	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Potassium	19.0	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Silicon	10.2	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	4/2/2020
Sodium	444	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Strontium	3.45	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-19	Customer sample ID: SSS2	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Barium	0.021	mg/L	10	0.001 (0.01)	4/3/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Boron 11	0.379	mg/L	10	0.005 (0.05)	4/3/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Copper 65	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	4/3/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200313
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/20/2020 11:47:13 AM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Lithium	0.153	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.010	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Silicon	10.8	mg/L	10	0.02	(0.2)	4/3/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Strontium	3.55	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Uranium	0.0057	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Vanadium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Zinc 66	0.0104	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-19	Customer sample ID: SSS2	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	ND	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/1/2020
Chloride	631	mg/L	10	1 (10)	4/1/2020
Fluoride	1.52	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/1/2020
Nitrate	0.51	mg NO3/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/1/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/1/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	5	0.5 (2.5)	4/1/2020
Sulfate	649	mg/L	10	1 (10)	4/1/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-19	Customer sample ID: SSS2	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	229	mg/L	1	5	3/24/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	280	mg/L	1	5	3/24/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	3/24/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200313
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/20/2020 11:47:13 AM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-19	Customer sample ID: SSS2	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	36.04	meq/L	1		
Cations total	35.19	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	-1.19	%	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-19	Customer sample ID: SSS2	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	770	mg CaCO3/ L	1		

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200313
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/20/2020 11:47:13 AM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-20	Customer sample ID: SSS3	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	3270	uS/cm	1		3/25/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-20	Customer sample ID: SSS3	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.4	ph Units	1		3/24/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-20	Customer sample ID: SSS3	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	172	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.02 (0.2)	4/2/2020
Magnesium	78.8	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Potassium	18.9	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Silicon	10.1	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	4/2/2020
Sodium	447	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Strontium	3.46	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-20	Customer sample ID: SSS3	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Barium	0.020	mg/L	10	0.001 (0.01)	4/3/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Boron 11	0.385	mg/L	10	0.005 (0.05)	4/3/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Copper 65	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	4/3/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200313
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/20/2020 11:47:13 AM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Lithium	0.153	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.010	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Silicon	11.0	mg/L	10	0.02	(0.2)	4/3/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Strontium	3.53	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Uranium	0.0056	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Vanadium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Zinc 66	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-20	Customer sample ID: SSS3	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	ND	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/1/2020
Chloride	635	mg/L	10	1 (10)	4/1/2020
Fluoride	1.51	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/1/2020
Nitrate	0.68	mg NO3/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/1/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/1/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	5	0.5 (2.5)	4/1/2020
Sulfate	652	mg/L	10	1 (10)	4/1/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-20	Customer sample ID: SSS3	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	220	mg/L	1	5	3/24/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	264	mg/L	1	5	3/24/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	3/24/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200313
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/20/2020 11:47:13 AM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-20	Customer sample ID: SSS3	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	36.02	meq/L	1		
Cations total	34.99	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	-1.45	%	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-20	Customer sample ID: SSS3	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	754	mg CaCO3/ L	1		

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200313
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/20/2020 11:47:13 AM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-21	Customer sample ID: SSS4	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	3220	uS/cm	1		3/25/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-21	Customer sample ID: SSS4	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.4	ph Units	1		3/24/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-21	Customer sample ID: SSS4	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	173	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.02 (0.2)	4/2/2020
Magnesium	78.8	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Potassium	18.9	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Silicon	10.5	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	4/2/2020
Sodium	439	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Strontium	3.40	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-21	Customer sample ID: SSS4	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Barium	0.021	mg/L	10	0.001 (0.01)	4/3/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Boron 11	0.386	mg/L	10	0.005 (0.05)	4/3/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Copper 65	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	4/3/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200313
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	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Lithium	0.151	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.010	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Silicon	10.9	mg/L	10	0.02	(0.2)	4/3/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Strontium	3.55	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Uranium	0.0058	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Vanadium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Zinc 66	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-21	Customer sample ID: SSS4	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	ND	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/1/2020
Chloride	638	mg/L	10	1 (10)	4/1/2020
Fluoride	1.58	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/1/2020
Nitrate	0.76	mg NO3/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/1/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/1/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	5	0.5 (2.5)	4/1/2020
Sulfate	656	mg/L	10	1 (10)	4/1/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-21	Customer sample ID: SSS4	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	228	mg/L	1	5	3/24/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	273	mg/L	1	5	3/24/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	3/24/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200313
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/20/2020 11:47:13 AM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-21	Customer sample ID: SSS4	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	36.33	meq/L	1		
Cations total	34.68	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	-2.32	%	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-21	Customer sample ID: SSS4	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	755	mg CaCO3/ L	1		

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200313
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/20/2020 11:47:13 AM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-22	Customer sample ID: SSS5	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	3230	uS/cm	1		3/25/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-22	Customer sample ID: SSS5	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.3	ph Units	1		3/24/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-22	Customer sample ID: SSS5	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	174	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.02 (0.2)	4/2/2020
Magnesium	78.2	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Potassium	18.8	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Silicon	10.2	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	4/2/2020
Sodium	437	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Strontium	3.39	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-22	Customer sample ID: SSS5	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Barium	0.021	mg/L	10	0.001 (0.01)	4/3/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Boron 11	0.386	mg/L	10	0.005 (0.05)	4/3/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Copper 65	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	4/3/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200313
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/20/2020 11:47:13 AM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Lithium	0.148	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.010	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Silicon	11.1	mg/L	10	0.02	(0.2)	4/3/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Strontium	3.57	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Uranium	0.0057	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Vanadium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Zinc 66	0.0105	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-22	Customer sample ID: SSS5	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	ND	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/1/2020
Chloride	637	mg/L	10	1 (10)	4/1/2020
Fluoride	1.54	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/1/2020
Nitrate	0.78	mg NO3/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/1/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/1/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	5	0.5 (2.5)	4/1/2020
Sulfate	653	mg/L	10	1 (10)	4/1/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-22	Customer sample ID: SSS5	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	228	mg/L	1	5	3/24/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	279	mg/L	1	5	3/24/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	3/24/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200313
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/20/2020 11:47:13 AM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-22	Customer sample ID: SSS5	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	36.26	meq/L	1		
Cations total	34.62	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	-2.32	%	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-22	Customer sample ID: SSS5	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	756	mg CaCO3/ L	1		

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200313
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/20/2020 11:47:13 AM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-23	Customer sample ID: SSS6	Test: Specific Conductance	Method: EPA 120.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Specific Conductance	3230	uS/cm	1		3/25/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-23	Customer sample ID: SSS6	Test: pH	Method: EPA 150.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
pH	8.2	ph Units	1		3/24/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-23	Customer sample ID: SSS6	Test: Cations by ICPOES	Method: EPA 200.7
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Calcium	175	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.02 (0.2)	4/2/2020
Magnesium	78.8	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Potassium	19.0	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Silicon	10.2	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	4/2/2020
Sodium	440	mg/L	10	0.05 (0.5)	4/2/2020
Strontium	3.42	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/2/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-23	Customer sample ID: SSS6	Test: Trace Metals by ICPMS	Method: EPA 200.8
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Aluminum	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Antimony 123	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Arsenic	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Barium	0.021	mg/L	10	0.001 (0.01)	4/3/2020
Beryllium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Boron 11	0.386	mg/L	10	0.005 (0.05)	4/3/2020
Cadmium 111	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Chromium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Cobalt	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Copper 65	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005 (0.005)	4/3/2020
Iron	ND	mg/L	10	0.01 (0.1)	4/3/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200313
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/20/2020 11:47:13 AM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Lead	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Lithium	0.152	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Manganese	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Molybdenum 95	0.010	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Nickel	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Selenium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Silicon	10.7	mg/L	10	0.02	(0.2)	4/3/2020
Silver 107	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Strontium	3.58	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Thallium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Thorium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Tin	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Titanium	ND	mg/L	10	0.001	(0.01)	4/3/2020
Uranium	0.0058	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Vanadium	ND	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020
Zinc 66	0.0129	mg/L	10	0.0005	(0.005)	4/3/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-23	Customer sample ID: SSS6	Test: Anions by IC	Method: EPA 300.0
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Bromide	ND	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/1/2020
Chloride	638	mg/L	10	1 (10)	4/1/2020
Fluoride	1.53	mg/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/1/2020
Nitrate	0.57	mg NO3/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/1/2020
Nitrite	ND	mg NO2/L	5	0.1 (0.5)	4/1/2020
Ortho Phosphate	ND	mg/L	5	0.5 (2.5)	4/1/2020
Sulfate	657	mg/L	10	1 (10)	4/1/2020

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-23	Customer sample ID: SSS6	Test: Alkalinity	Method: EPA 310.1
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Alkalinity as CaCO3	230	mg/L	1	5	3/24/2020
Bicarbonate (HCO3)	281	mg/L	1	5	3/24/2020
Carbonate (CO3)	ND	mg/L	1	5	3/24/2020

Customer: National Cave and Karst Research Institute (NCKRI)	Order Number: 200313
Contact: Lewis Land	Receive Date: 3/20/2020 11:47:13 AM
Phone: 575-689-6517	Project:
	Matrix: Water

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-23	Customer sample ID: SSS6	Test: Checking correctness	Method: SM 1030E
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Anions total	36.43	meq/L	1		
Cations total	34.82	meq/L	1		
Percent difference	-2.26	%	1		

Laboratory sample ID: 200313-23	Customer sample ID: SSS6	Test: Hardness by calculation	Method: SM 2340B
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Parameter	Result	Units	Dilution	Reporting limit	Analysis Date
Hardness	761	mg CaCO3/ L	1		